

EXPERIENCES IN PREVENTING OFFENSES AMONG YOUTH IN UZBEKISTAN

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In today's complex and precarious times, living in harmony with the rapidly changing era requires that we do not limit ourselves to the achievements we have gained, but rather avoid complacency and strive for new heights. It is essential to continuously seek progress and advance along the path of development and renewal. In this context, it can be said that alongside the achievements, there are still significant issues awaiting resolution regarding enhancing the effectiveness of crime prevention among youth. There is a need to address the problems and shortcomings arising in the organizational and legal regulation of crime prevention among youth, as well as to develop recommendations aimed at enriching its scientific and theoretical foundations. The global community is increasingly concerned about implementing effective policies to combat crime. In this regard, protecting individuals, their rights and freedoms, societal and state interests, property, the natural environment, peace, and humanity from criminal aggression, as well as establishing a modern and effective system for crime prevention, are becoming increasingly global and urgent issues.

Indeed, criminological studies indicate that by improving preventive measures, it is possible to prevent seven out of every ten crimes.

It is important to emphasize that the real goal is not just to put an end to offenses among youth, but rather to prevent them at an early stage and reduce the incidence of such offenses to the lowest possible level.

This is because offenses are a socially dangerous, socio-legal phenomenon that exists at every stage of societal development. Therefore, it cannot be said that offenses will completely disappear at a certain stage of human development.

In this regard, the view of Russian scholar Yu.M. Antonyan that "crime cannot be completely eradicated; it can only be reduced along with society" and the opinions of Uzbek scholars X.T. Odilqoriev and I.T. Tulteev that "the goal of completely eliminating crime in the fight against it is unrealistic; the state of crime and the ten conditions for combating it show that sometimes it is effective,

and sometimes it is ineffective. It seems that completely eradicating crime is an extremely complex and entirely unattainable dream" are fully justified.

The issues surrounding the legal provision of preventive activities against offenses among youth have become one of the most important matters today. Indeed, effective management of this area requires regular analysis and monitoring of the legal frameworks governing it, as well as observing how well they align with and are implemented in social life.

Analysis of practical results shows that currently, the compliance with the requirements of legislative documents regulating preventive activities against offenses among youth is not at a satisfactory level. For instance, according to paragraph 7 of the regulation approved by the order No. 193 of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 6, 2017, the report provided by the preventive inspector in the neighborhood citizen assemblies is carried out in five main areas, three of which—60%—are comprised of the results of preventive work conducted among minors and youth.

In general, we believe that the establishment of a system for regular reporting by preventive inspectors in front of the population and the development of clear criteria for evaluating the work done contribute positively to: Firstly, the effectiveness of the activities of internal affairs bodies, particularly in the prevention of offenses among youth;

Secondly, ensuring openness, transparency, and legality in their operations. Considering that the internal affairs bodies have a large number of personnel within the law enforcement system and possess specialized services and institutions that conduct social prevention with minors, they play a significant role in implementing the prevention of offenses among youth. In recent years, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev has stated that "the internal affairs, prosecutor's office, Youth Union, Women's Committee, neighborhood committees, and other state and non-governmental organizations must take timely measures to prevent unemployment, drug addiction, neglect, family disputes, and similar issues that contribute to crime and offenses. Moreover, there should be a focus on avoiding generalizations, striving towards a common goal, collaborating effectively, and addressing each problem based on a clear plan."

These ideological views have ensured the systematic development and implementation of inter-agency programs for the prevention of offenses among

youth, taking into account specificity in targeting, sectoral specialization, regional characteristics, and other unique aspects.

As a result, the effectiveness of addressing social problems among youth has increased. In particular, efforts have been intensified to ensure their employment, engage them in socially beneficial activities, and organize their leisure time meaningfully. In this regard, the requirements for individuals appointed to the position of preventive inspector have been strengthened. Necessary measures have been taken to create suitable working conditions for them.

In conclusion, ensuring the prevention of offenses among youth in the current circumstances is a key direction of legal policy. It is aimed at eradicating the roots of criminality and serves as a primary method of providing a preventive impact on criminogenic factors at the early stages of their development. The ultimate result of prevention allows society, especially with minimal costs, to address the tasks of combating criminality

References:

1. Зиёдуллаев М.З. Ички ишлар органларининг таянч пунктларини бошқаришни такомиллаштириш: Юридик фанлар доктори диссертацияси. - Т.: 2019. - Б. 96
2. Исмаилов И. Вояга етмаганлар жиноятчилигининг криминологик тавсифи ва профилактикаси // Криминология. Махсус кием: Дарслик / Муаллифлар жамоаси. — Т.: 2015. — Б. 26-27.
3. Камалова Д.Г. Жиноятга тайёргарлик куришнинг хусусиятлари ва унинг учун жавобгарликни такомиллаштириш: Юридик фанлар буйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси автореферати. - Т.: 2018.
4. Каримов И.А. Эришган марралар билан чегараланмасдан, бошлаган ислохотларимизни янги кўтариш - бугунги кундаги энг долзарб вазирамиздир. Ж. 23. - Т.: 2015. Б. 110
5. Одилқориев Х.Т., Тультеев И.Т. Жинойи-ҳуқуқий сиёсатни либераллаштириш: зарурат ва омиллар // Ҳуқуқ-Право-Law. - 2002. - № 1.
6. Теоретические основы предупреждения преступности. - М.: 1977. 30-31.
7. Ўзбекистон Республикаси ички ишлар вазирининг 2017 йил 6 сентябрдаги 193-сон «Ички ишлар органлари таянч пунктлари профилактика инспекторларининг хисоботини фуқаролар йигинларида эшитиш тартиби тўғрисидаги низомни тасдиқлаш ҳақида»ги буйруғи
8. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг 2017 йил 20 ноябрь куни ўтказилган жиноятчиликка қарши курашиш ва

хуқуқбузарликларнинг олдини олишда давлат ва жамоат ташкилотлари ҳамкорлигига батишланган йиғилишда сўзлаган нутки // Халқ сўзи. — 2017. — 21 ноябр.

